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MEDICAL TOURISM IN SURKHANDARYO

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Abstract: *The article deal with the medical tourism in Surkhandaryo region in Uzbekistan. That is to say, 2 main medical touristic areas in this region having been beneficial and natural treatment area for local and international tourists for many years.*

Keywords: *Surkhandaryo, tourism, medical treatment, some allergic diseases, natural salt cave.*

Introduction: There are various types of tourism in the world with medical tourism being the most important one. Medical tourism in Uzbekistan has made significant strides in the last decade alone and today has much to offer. As modern medical centers are equipped with high-qualified specialists, including but not limited foreign and English physicans. Medical tourism is developing day-bye-day in all regions in our country offering acupuncture, homeopathic cures and massage therapy.

There are some medical tourist areas in Surkhandaryo in which regional and international people can go to be well-being. One of which is “Khojaykon” natural salt cave. This is an amazing place, being in which is healthy, unusual and interesting. In total, there are five similar speleological clinics in the CIS countries. The main effect of the Khodjaikon cave is achieved due to the concentration of salt and light negative aerons in the air, which has a beneficial effect in the treatment of

pulmonological diseases. The treatment procedure in the cave takes about 2-2.5 hours a day. The unique microclimate, which is achieved with the help of constant temperature and humidity, is the purest air environment, without allowing air infection. The Khodjaikon salt cave is located on the southeastern slope of the foothills of the Kugitangtau ridge in the Sherabad district of Surkhandarya region and is located at an altitude of 1200 meters above sea level. It was opened in 1989 and externally represents a large salt monolith, inside of which there is a system of galleries. Inside the galleries there are five treatment rooms-chambers that differ from each other in temperature, humidity, pressure and trace elements. The walls of the cave are uniquely covered with a layer of salt from one to three centimeters, in the passage there is a spring containing a saline. For many years, many people have been visiting this area to cure. In this cave environment, there are useful supplements in the treatment of allergic diseases of the respiratory tract, long-lasting acute and chronic bronchitis, asthma, pneumonia complications and skin diseases. The essence of treatment is finding salt deposits in caves and mines the cleanest air environment with no possibility of air pollution. There is a magnificent panoramic view of the Surkhandarya Mountains. Also, not far from the "Khodjaikon" you can see salt lakes. A unique microclimate achieved with constant temperature and humidity makes the temperature is 7-27 degrees, the relative humidity is 50-70 percent and the atmospheric pressure is kept around 700 mm of mercury. The air contains elements such as magnesium, potassium, iron hydroxide and about twenty other trace elements. In addition, many therapy treatments have been held in this area.

One of the medical tourist areas in Surkhandarya is Omonkhona. Omonkhona is a village belonging to Boysun district of Surkhandarya region and it is located 16 kilometers from the center of the district in which it is surrounded by hills. The nature is calm with fresh air atmosphere. More than a thousand people and 150 households have been living in the village for many years. There is a healing spring in the village, the numerous of tourists visit it and there is a 160-bed sanatorium of the joint-stock company "Uzbekistan Railways" in the village. Under the

chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2023 - at the video selector meeting held on June 7, it was mentioned that the road infrastructure will be improved in the village of Omonkhona, more than 200 service facilities will be built along the road, and at least a thousand jobs will be created a year, The presence of silicic acid, iron, aluminum and many other trace elements in the spring water was found. According to experts, useful compounds in water have the properties of treating the liver and gall bladder.

In 2018, spring water was started to be packaged by the factory. This work was carried out by "Uzbekistan Railways" JSC. According to inquiries, it was found that the local population was involved in this work in an unethical manner and their activities were stopped. Omonkhona sanatorium People from different regions of Uzbekistan come to this area for treatment due to the healing properties of the spring water of Omonkhona. For this reason, the sanatorium "Omonkhona" was established in this area, and according to the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in October

Omonkhona's water is unique in Central Asia in terms of its composition and effect on the human body. The main basis of treatment at the "Omonkhona" balneological treatment center is drinking and taking a bath in this sulphide mineral water. In addition to this, dozens of treatment services such as massage, diagnostics, ultrasound, electrotherapy, and phytotherapy are available at the health center. In addition to the modern "Omonkhona" treatment center belonging to the joint-stock company of Uzbekistan Railways, there is also one more modern hotel including 9 family guest houses, and a medicinal water packaging enterprise operating in this area.

Conclusion: The medical tourism is a profitable source of income for the budget of the region thus, many countries are paying attention for the improvements of medical tourism. It is more effective to develop medical tourism than other types of tourism. Because this is live advertising, that is to say, after people having been cured, they say all of their relatives or friends about it that when they visited in

Uzbekistan to treat and the effect of those treatments was effective. Medical tourism is one of the none-seasonal tourism. As people always get sick and they use medical tourism. In this regard, provided that we advance the medical tourism, it can be useful for the budget of the country as well as the health of people in the world.

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